

Deliverable D7.1.

Communication and dissemination plan

ERA FABRIC

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Executive summary

The purpose of this Deliverable D7.1 is to provide a vision and present detailed implementation approach regarding the communication, dissemination and exploitation of the project, in compliance with EU and Horizon Europe regulations and strategies, with specific reference to the Research Area. This concerns the work done in the Work Package 7 – Communication, Dissemination and Public Engagement and all project activities and content delivery process.

Table of content

Executive summary	2
Table of content	3
Abbreviations	5
Introduction.....	6
Communication & dissemination strategy.....	7
Purpose (“why?”)	7
Messages (“what?”)	13
Brand and project recognition creation	13
Key audiences (“who?”)	13
Method (“how?”)	15
ERA FABRIC Communication Plan	16
ERA FABRIC Dissemination Plan	18
Work package WP7 – Communication, Dissemination and Public Engagement	20
ERA FABRIC Communication and Dissemination Plan Impact	23
Deliverables & Milestones.....	25
Time (“when?”)	26
Gender and equal treatment aspects	27
Compliance with ethical principles and relevant legislations (GDPR).....	28
Ethical principles.....	28
Ethical dimension of the objectives, methodology and likely impact and GDPR compliance	28
Compliance with GDPR will be ensured at all times.	29
Data Processing	30
Personal Data Protection Compliance.....	31
Privacy accountability.....	31
Sharing of the collected data with the Project Partners	31
Personal data collection through forms and Privacy Notices	31
References.....	33
ANNEX 1. ERA FABRIC project visualization	35
Logotypes	35
Project Logotypes	35
EU logotypes.....	36
Partner logotypes	37
Templates.....	37
Documents	37
Presentation	38
ANNEX 2. ERA FABRIC WWW Platform	41
Structure.....	41
Technology	42
WWW Hosting	42
Newsletter.....	43
Calendar	43
Analytics	43

Print screens	44
ANNEX 3. Social media	45
LinkedIn	45
Twitter	46
YouTube.....	47
ANNEX 4. Events calendar	48
ANNEX 5. Communication activities time schedule	49
ANNEX 6. Dissemination activities time schedule.....	50
ANNEX 7. KPIs monitoring tool.....	51

Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
COM	Communication
DL	Deliverable Leader
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Areas
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
MS	Member State
PC	Project Coordinator
PP	Project partner
R&D	Research & Development
R&I	Research & Innovation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights

Introduction

Overarching aim of the ERA FABRIC project is to define, structure, populate and validate the “interconnected knowledge space” foreseen by the EU ERA Hubs initiative (COM 2020 628 final). Three distinct, and intertwined, dimensions, all of them relevant for policy making, are adopted as a structuring principle for the community to be built and cultivated during the project:

- 1) ERA Hubs as Knowledge Ecosystems which foster the dynamic interaction of R&D and innovation actors at regional and multiregional levels, taking into account the different knowledge and cultural contexts and the alignment of research foci and industrial needs;
- 2) ERA Hubs as Multi Stakeholder Platforms which bring together the representatives of the various involved interest groups in a seamless and uninterrupted discussion and deliberation on strategic priorities, actions and results evaluation;
- 3) ERA Hubs as a Policy Co Creation Toolbox which are a transformative set of measures and tools operating in a “middle ground” needing to be configured as a distinct space from both the EU and the MS/Regional levels, historically presided over by “ad hoc” sets of instruments (e.g. Framework Programmes for R&I, Structural and Investment Funds, Interregional and Cross Border Cooperation Programmes).

It is the consortium’s vision and assumption that the 3 above dimensions should be presided over and made interoperable, in order for the ERA Hubs initiative to become path breaking and impactful at broad EU level. ERA FABRIC is designed by leading European actors in the domain of regional development. The 11 partners represent 8 Member States and 1 Associated State. With the addition of the letters of interest gathered before the proposal presentation, almost half of EU27 territorial coverage has been reached.

The communication, dissemination and public engagement ERA FABRIC activities aim at the diffusion of the project’s results beyond the consortium and the direct stakeholders, maximising the project’s contribution to innovation and inviting a wide range of stakeholders to embrace and benefit from the project’s advancements. This document presents the scope of these activities.

Communication & dissemination strategy

The communication and dissemination plan addresses the following elements:

- Purpose (“why?”)
- Messages (“what?”)
- Key audiences (“who?”)
- Methods (“how?”)
- Time (“when?”)

Purpose (“why?”)

The aim of ERA FABRIC is to support the ongoing process of creation of a European network of ERA Hubs, by helping to define, structure and populate the “interconnected knowledge space” foreseen by the EU ERA Hubs initiative. Its specific impacts are to:

- Providing support for policy makers in addressing the need for better analysis and evidence, including simplifying and facilitating the inter-play between national and European R&I systems.
- Improve access to excellence and increasing the performance of R&I systems. Giving emphasis to dedicated Horizon Europe measures as well as complementarities with smart specialisation strategies under the Cohesion Policy.
- Translating R&I results into the economy. R&I policies should aim to boost the resilience and competitiveness of our economies and societies.
- Underpinning a new ERA benefiting from knowledge creation, circulation and use. This empowers higher education institutions and research organisations to embrace a transformative process. It enables a highly skilled workforce to circulate freely. It ensures research outputs are shared. It assures gender equality. It makes it so that the outcomes of R&I are understood, trusted and increasingly used, by educated informed scientists and citizens to the benefit of society.
- Prioritise investments and reforms to accelerate the green and digital transformation and to increase competitiveness as well as the speed and depth of the recovery (indirect).

The activities of the project will lead to achievement of 10 operational objectives. They include several details sub-objectives (*Table 1*). This effort is expected to provide visible successful outputs and outcomes which will illustrate the boost of Renewed ERA, particularly in the specific project thematic domains: Sustainable manufacturing, Biobased circular economy and Clean renewable energy.

Table 1. ERA FABRIC objectives and evidence of success

Operational objective	Sub-objectives	Evidence of success	Involved WPs
Enlist and engage an EU-wide population of Quadruple Helix actors and stakeholders in the co-design of the ERA FABRIC community of interest.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage actors and stakeholders in each of the participant territories to build and maintain local communities of interest. Involve local communities in parallel working groups, capacity building initiatives, needs analyses, co-design, monitoring and evaluation activities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 9 regional/local communities of at least 50 participants each. At least 8 meetings (1 per quarter) per each working group. At least 6 capacity building webinars for the whole project. At least 9 short videos of testimonials reporting about their experiences and perceived benefits (1 per region). 	WP3 WP5 WP7
Schedule a plan of P2P learning events (both online and offline) to ensure a true and consistent exchange of knowledge among the project partners and with their community members (notably including civil society).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define (already at kick-off) a tentative list of private (closed-door) and public gatherings (both directly organized and from relevant third parties) to be attended by the project partners. Ensure a broad participation of local actors and stakeholders (if needed, by appropriate translation of proceedings) to each partner's public event(s). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> At least 8 public events (1 per quarter) in combination with the periodic consortium meetings. At least 9 ecosystem profiles. At least 20 individual partner attendances to third party events (e.g. policy workshops or academic conferences). At least 500 non-unique individual attendances from local actors and stakeholders. 	WP 4 WP 7

Operational objective	Sub-objectives	Evidence of success	Involved WPs
<p>Exploit the existing, EU-wide and international networks of the consortium members to raise the awareness and increase the visibility of the ERA FABRIC project, its aims and achievements.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attribute (already at kick-off) to each partner an average number of 2 additional regions or countries, prioritising those that are not represented in the consortium. • Establish a continuous flow of communication with actors and stakeholders from these regions for the entire project duration. • Liaise with the sister project(s) of this call, existing and upcoming ERA Hubs, and other EU initiatives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • At least 10 additional territories covered with formal alliances. • At least 100 individual attendances to project events from actors and stakeholders not belonging to the consortium. • At least 500 recipients of the ERA FABRIC policy brief newsletters. • At least 10 other projects and initiatives clustered. 	<p>WP 7</p>
<p>Explore and substantiate with field evidence the concept of ERA Hubs as Knowledge Ecosystems.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deliver a state of the art analysis of knowledge ecology as a territorial production factor, including a census of related experiences and good practice examples. • Run a EU-wide stakeholder survey on the most recurrent characteristics of knowledge ecosystems and assess the degree of conformance of partner regions to the ideal type. • Develop a self-assessment and guidance tools for regions aiming to verify their strategic alignment to the model. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 online publication. • 1 survey exercise with at least 100 respondents. • 1 online self-assessment tool with at least 100 checked profiles. 	<p>WP 2 WP 7</p>

Operational objective	Sub-objectives	Evidence of success	Involved WPs
Develop and structure a real-life instantiation of the concept of ERA Hubs as Multi Stakeholder Platform.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Liaise with regional and local actors, stakeholders and communities from both within and outside the consortium to deliver a needs analysis as well as a gap analysis of their existing policies and instruments. • Form thematic working groups at local level, connected with parallel activities in the other partner sites, on three main topics of interest for the consortium. • Set up the project's capacity building infrastructure for policy makers and other interested stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 9 need and gap analyses (1 per partner location). • 3 thematic working groups at project level (with instances at each partner site) on the topic of sustainable manufacturing, • biobased circular economy and clean renewable energy. • 1 syllabus and IT infrastructure for the delivery of webinars. • 1 collection of governance rules and arrangements. 	WP 3 WP 7
Select a combination of existing (proven) and innovative (yet to be tested) instruments for the implementation of the concept of ERA Hubs' Policy Co Creation Toolbox.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structure the activity of the thematic working groups on four main priority areas for policy innovation, as explained below in this proposal (T4.1 through T4.4). • Organise the results of the three working groups according to the four areas with a summary of the transformative potential of the ERA Hubs "middle ground" model. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 sections of the Policy toolbox. • At least 10 meaningful case studies per section. • At least 5 tested instruments per section / collection of case studies • At least 1 innovative instrument proposed per section • 1 theory of change of the ERA Hubs model. 	WP3 WP4

Operational objective	Sub-objectives	Evidence of success	Involved WPs
Monitor and evaluate the project activities and their results, including gender balance and standardisation potential.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define a methodology for impact and outcome evaluation, based on the theory of change. • Deliver two rounds of data collection and interpretation, notably including gender balance. • Assess feasibility of a quality label and standardisation approach. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 methodology and plan of monitoring and evaluation activities. • At least 40 interviews and 2 evaluation surveys involving no fewer than 120 participants. • 1 feasibility study for a quality label of ERA Hubs. 	WP5 WP1
Define a replicable model for ERA Hubs as Knowledge Ecosystems, Multi Stakeholder Platform, and Policy Toolbox.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote a wide reflection on key widening and sustainability related aspects of the ERA Hubs model. • Build a taxonomy of ERA Hub schemes with related profiles and implications for policy. • Draw lessons and policy recommendations, particularly for the next generation of ERA Hubs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 ERA FABRIC policy briefs. • 1 classification of ERA Hub schemes. • 1 business plan and road map for the post-grant phase. 	WP6 WP7

Operational objective	Sub-objectives	Evidence of success	Involved WPs
<p>Communicate and disseminate project activities and results to accompany the development of the ERA FABRIC community towards its impact targets</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define and maintain a professional graphic design and communication strategy. • Communicate effectively within the consortium and with the external actors and stakeholders. • Develop a project web platform and news feed representing the consortium and its achievements, as a first step towards the official ERA Hubs platform. • Disseminate project results to scientific and sectoral targets and channels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broad international visibility of the consortium and the ERA FABRIC image. • Single message for the vision and mission shared internally and in the participant communities. • Project web platform and news feed with 15,000 visitors by project end. • Publication of at least 5 articles and papers on refereed journals and in conference proceedings. 	<p>WP7</p>
<p>Carry out effective project management to ensure smooth and risk free operations and meeting project objectives, including gender balance.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensure quality management, including an initial quality handbook and continuing with risk assessment and the production of 6-monthly internal Progress Reports. • Strategic project coordination and Advisory Board engagement in guiding and evaluating project activities. • Professional technical management and reporting to the Commission. • Governance and Steering Committee meetings, with the drawing up of a Consortium • Agreement and management of project/contractual issues as required. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low number of incidences of tensions or conflict between partners. • Degree of originality and rigour coherent with project objectives. • Timely delivery of project results within budgets and targets. • Strategic coherence with the directions of the EU ERA Hubs and related initiatives. • External Advisory Board composed of at least 5 internationally renowned experts. 	<p>WP 1</p>

Messages (“what?”)

Brand and project recognition creation

During the first phase of the project, ERA FABRIC's main messages will be of a more general nature to build a 'brand', create awareness of the project and its goals, and engage relevant stakeholders. As the project starts to generate results, general messages will be accompanied by specific messages promoting the results and other activities, still aimed at strengthening the ERA FABRIC brand and ultimately increasing the impact of the project and the working group.

As part of "building a recognisable brand" will be created that will be consistently referred to in communication about the project. Social media of the project and a dedicated website are also being created, which will allow for extensive communication and reaching all target groups. In addition, appropriate hashtags will be created, which will allow to expand the group of recipients of messages about the project's results during the project.

While the main goals of ERA FABRIC's branding, visibility and impact will remain the same for the duration of the project, the message content and target audience may change slightly as the phases of the project evolve.

Key audiences (“who?”)

ERA FABRIC will target 7 groups of audience. Their participation in the project is motivated different interests in the project . This impose on the communication and dissemination activities the need to adapt the tuned interaction and engagement measure the most relevant to each of them (*Table 2*).

Table 2. Dissemination and Exploitation Target Groups

Groups	Target audience	Interest in the project	Approach
A – Industry 4.0, Smart Cities, Smart Energy, Bio Agriculture domain actors at local/regional and national/EU levels	Professional experts Entrepreneurs Startuppwers Intermediary organisations Private investors Venture capitalists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support project activities via active participation in the working groups • Get inspired for new ideas, services, and applications • Participate in project’s engagement, capacity building and dissemination activities • Use shared infrastructures and services • Join the project’s capacity building, dissemination and evaluation activities and events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Participation in the expert policy meetings, conferences.</i> • <i>Active presence on the social media channels</i>

Groups	Target audience	Interest in the project	Approach
B - Actors from Research performing organisation, Research infrastructures and e-Infrastructures belonging to the ERA	<p>Researchers Academics Technical staff Administrative staff Supporting subcontractors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support project activities via active participation in the working groups • Enhance assets' recognizability • Definition of future research and innovation directions • Help with removing barriers/framework conditions • Join the project's capacity building, dissemination and evaluation activities and events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Participation in the scientific conferences.</i> • <i>Active presence in the scientific networks and forums</i>
C - Civil Society and Educational actors at local/regional and national levels	<p>Professional associations Business associations Districts/Clusters Professional & High schools NGOs (e.g. Environmental)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support project activities via active participation in the working groups • Stay tuned with emerging policy trends and opportunities • Develop new value-adding services for their associates/beneficiaries • Help with indicating how to remove barriers/improve framework conditions • Join the project's capacity building, dissemination and evaluation activities and events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Participation in the business and cluster conferences.</i> • <i>Active presence in the business and networks and forums.</i>
D - Policy makers, Civil servants, Financial organisations and Standardisation bodies	<p>Policy makers and Civil servants from Cities, Regions, Ministries and the EC Bankers Donors Standard setting bureau Members</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support project activities via active participation in the working groups • Utilise project's results in everyday operations • Help with indicating how to remove barriers/improve framework conditions • Join the project's capacity building, dissemination and evaluation activities and events • Revise/improve existing policies and strategies based on acquired knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Participation in the policy gatherings and public consultations</i>

Groups	Target audience	Interest in the project	Approach
E – Related Projects, Networks and Initiatives	EARTO EEN ERRIN EURADA Vanguard Initiative Etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of common topics • Synergies and collaborations for results promotion • Enhance innovation through results' combination • Define of future research and innovation directions based on acquired knowledge • Inputs for standardisation activities • Co-organisation of events 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Participation in the networking activities and events of this associations</i> • <i>Following them on the social media</i>
F – Social media and Press	Participants in the project's social media groups. Journalists General public and anyone interested in the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand the vision and mission of ERA FABRIC project • Be informed about and take part in the activities of the project • Be engaged in future activities at local level (post-project) such as citizen science 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Strategic alliances with media houses like Business Science</i> • <i>Active presence on the social media channels</i>

Method (“how?”)

Communication activities include all actions that contribute to the diffusion of the project's results beyond the consortium and the direct stakeholders, maximising the project's contribution to innovation and inviting a wide range of stakeholders to embrace and benefit from the project's advancements. In this direction, the project includes (Figure 1):

- Define concrete measurable objectives for communication activities for the appropriate target groups;
- Define guidelines for communication and dissemination actions (e.g., project identity, messages to convey, internal reporting rules, etc.);
- Implement a modern inclusive communication strategy and action plan to reach these objectives; set up the different channels, tools and mechanisms for the communication plan and targeted audiences;
- Measure communication impact, apply corrective actions and identify new opportunities to maximise visibility;
- Collect relevant documentation related to the achievement of communication KPIs

Figure 1. Dissemination & Communication ERA FABRIC process

ERA FABRIC Communication Plan

ERA FABRIC communication objectives have been already defined and they are directly linked to the project dissemination phases: raise awareness, inform and interact, promote (Figure 2).

Figure 2. ERA FABRIC Communication Plan – objectives

ERA FABRIC project will not only create awareness among potential adopters/users in the general public about its concept, goals, results through key messages in communication material, but it will also activate a community of potential users and collect feedback.

Furthermore, it will focus on targeted groups to exploit the project's results in the industry and society.

The above objectives will be reached through the following communication activities (Figure 3).

Figure 3. ERA FABRIC Communication Plan – activities

ERA FABRIC web platform (www.erafabric.eu) is the main tool to communicate with stakeholders. It is designed & developed as an intuitive and responsive web platform which includes search engine optimisation. The web platform content will be regularly updated and the analytics are employed to measure impact and provide content of interest. The platform will provide a clear visibility of results, demo/application material in an interactive way.

The second communication channels are social media. The presence in [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#), [ResearchGate Lab](#), [YouTube](#) has been established. The channels will reproduce relevant content and monitor relevant hashtags, also upload public material. They follow influencers of the project domain and will engage to other projects and initiatives. The channels will allow for interactions with followers to get feedback, answers on comments and private messages.

Project's news will be mainly posted at ERA FABRIC web, but posts to EU publication (e.g. Cordis News, EU Research magazines and external journal) will be sent. The project partners will deploy news feed which will be related to project's positioning and interim

achievements. The posts will try to initiate discussions on specific issues relevant to the project to receive feedback.

The communication package includes traditional media., the press release will announce the project's launch and progress, significant events/results and the policy value and societal benefits of the project's results.

To support the communication and dissemination activities the project logo & graphic has been designed. Furthermore a brochure, a leaflet, a first policy brief and a promotional video will be prepared.

For detailed timing see ANNEX 3.

ERA FABRIC Dissemination Plan

The dissemination strategy to be applied in the project is aligned to the following objectives (Figure 4). The dissemination activities will deal with the diffusion of knowledge generated within the context of the project, aiming to ensure both a mid- and long-term impact by informing the European target audiences.

Figure 4. ERA FABRIC Dissemination Plan – objectives

The dissemination project's activities will ensure maximum visibility of the project in the target audiences via appropriate key messages which will include the knowledge generated within and beyond the project's consortium. The project will establish liaisons with other projects and initiatives for knowledge and innovation production, transfer and uptake. The engagement of the targeted audiences will allow for getting feedback and validate the project's results. The project will try to attract potential adopters and

stimulate the appropriate target segments to support the project’s exploitation strategy and encourage the development of further outcomes in new initiatives. The achievement of the objective will be supported by the implementation of the following dissemination activities (Figure 5).

Figure 5. ERA FABRIC Dissemination Plan – activities.

Organisation of public events both offline and online	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation of workshops/seminars alongside project meetings • Organisation of workshops/seminars and training events (webinars)
Participation in third party events (EU and national policy gatherings)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentation of project scope; Interaction with participants. • Presentation of project results; Interaction with participants.
Participation in scientific conferences and academic events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication of position papers; Organisation of special sessions. • Publication of interim results; Organisation of special sessions.
Community Building/ Engagement with local stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of thematic working groups. • Discussions within the thematic working groups; sharing of early results. • Video demonstrations of activities and sharing of the final project results.
Collaboration and Synergies with sister Projects and ERA Hubs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Synergy identification; establishment of contact points; exchange of ideas & intentions. • Periodic bilateral exchange of news & results, joint presence at events. • Joint engagement in events and initiatives.
Internal dissemination through Partners Networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project's links & news in partners' websites, social media accounts, newsletters. • Inclusion of project' results in partners' events. • Demonstration of use of results in partners' regions.
Contributions to standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State of the art analysis. • Definition of criteria and conditions for quality assessment. • Finalisation and public presentation of the quality scheme.

Within the project framework, public events – both offline and online, workshops/seminars alongside project meetings and workshops/seminars and training events will be organised.

The project partners representative will participate in third party events (EU and national policy gatherings like EBN or the Annual Research Conference 2023) to present project scope and results and to interact with participants. Furthermore, the dissemination agenda foresee participation in scientific conferences and academic events, publication of position papers and interim results, organisation of special sessions.

The project will build community of interest and practice with local stakeholders by creating thematic working groups allowing for discussion and sharing of early results. The video demonstrations of activities and sharing of the final project results will increase the accessibility of the project outcomes.

The project foresee the set up of collaboration and synergies with COOPERATE projects which is in parallel testing ERA Hubs concept. The process includes identification of

synergies, establishment of contact points, exchange of ideas & intentions, joint presence at events and initiatives.

To support the project's dissemination activities the partners will process internal dissemination through partners' Networks. To enforce the project posts will be linked to news in partners' websites, social media accounts, newsletters, inclusion of project' results in partners' events and finally demonstration of use of results in partners' regions.

The ambition of ERA FABRIC project is contributing to standards through state of the art ecosystem standards analysis, definition of criteria and conditions for quality assessment and finalisation and public presentation of the quality scheme.

Work package WP7 – Communication, Dissemination and Public Engagement

The WP7 coordinates the communication, dissemination and public engagement actions of the project as outlined in Sections 1 and 2, which constitute the essence of ERA FABRIC outward looking strategy as a Coordination and Support Action (Table 3).

Table 3. Work package WP7 – Communication, Dissemination and Public Engagement

Tasks name, timing and responsibility	Description
<p>Task 7.1: Communication and dissemination planning and monitoring Lead: WUT Timing: M01-M06 Partners involved: ALL except NTNU</p>	<p>This Task identifies the key messages, targets and channels and draws up the Communication and Dissemination Plan as outlined in Sec on 2.2. Activities here include both the planning and scheduling of the local events (at partner sites) and the international ones described in Sec on 1.1 among the project objectives. They also include setting up of a monitoring exercise to see their status and taking stock of progress and achievements.</p>
<p>Task 7.2: Visibility and outreach generation approaches, tools and materials Lead: WUT Timing: M01-M24 Partners involved: ALL except NTNU</p>	<p>This Task covers the delivery of the logo and brand image of the project (including communication guidelines and templates of deliverables, PowerPoint presentations, letterhead, roll-ups, etc.) as well as the following tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project web platform and news feed (in EN) - They will be created to be the ensure a visible presence of ERA FABRIC on the Internet, providing general information about the project, its advances, multimedia contents (brochures, videos), news and posts to state current developments and updates as they emerge; • E-brochure and E-leaflet - to support the awareness and promotion of ERA FABRIC, its vision and concept. This material will be in English and also translated in the languages of the consortium (CZ, DE, ES, HR, IT, NO, PL, PT, RO) and others as appropriate to support public presentations and events (workshops, seminars, webinars);

Tasks name, timing and responsibility	Description
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 Policy Briefs with reports of major project achievements; • Creation of ERA FABRIC social media accounts (in EN) on LinkedIn, ResearchGate, Twitter and YouTube.
<p>Task 7.3: Awareness raising and bringing science closer to citizens Lead: UNIST Timing: M01-M24 Partners involved: ALL except NTNU</p>	<p>The consortium will consider the possibility of synergizing with new and existing projects, funded by national and European sources, to achieve one of the priority targets of the ERA Hub model that is a diffused engagement of citizens. At project start and recurrently across time, each partner will identify potential synergy projects and join forces with them to carry out such dissemination. For instance, at UNIST there is the European Researcher Night every year, a Science festival every spring (implemented on national level in different cities), and other running projects (SEAEU, ReSEArch-EU, etc.) which run activities aimed at citizens (i.e. living labs, transformation labs, Hackathons, etc.).</p>
<p>Task 7.4: Networking with other ERA Hubs Lead: ECOPLUS Timing: M07-M24 Partners involved: ALL except NTNU</p>	<p>This task addresses KER #12, i.e. the establishment of permanent relations with the sister project(s) funded by the same HE Call, new and emerging ERA Hubs and other EU initiatives such as Digital Innovation Hubs. At least 1 meeting per semester will be organised to ensure interaction and communication with the sister project(s) while ERA Hubs and DIHs will be kept informed of the various initiatives organised by the consortium as per Section 1.1 and T7.1 above.</p>
<p>Task 7.5: Synergies with other EU initiatives Lead: CNR Timing: M01-M24 Partners involved: ALL except NTNU</p>	<p>Synergies with other initiatives such as European University Alliances, EIT KICs, Enterprise Europe Network, European Digital Innovation Hubs, TEFs, Smart Specialisation Platform, EURAXESS, ERA4You, Horizon Europe ERN etc. will be guaranteed. These connections will be facilitated thanks to direct involvement of many ERA FABRIC partners in the abovementioned initiatives and projects, as documented in Table 1.3. Synergies will also be created with recent initiatives such as the Partnership for Regional Innovation-PRI, as well as with the Thematic Partnerships built within the Smart Specialisation Platform.</p>

Sharing communication responsibilities

While WUT will coordinate communication and dissemination activities, close collaboration with project partners will be key to ensuring maximum outreach and therefore impact. A process to disseminate the project's messages through all partners' tools and channels will be established. In order to support the partners' dissemination

efforts, a short communication guide will be created and updated throughout the project, which will include a detailed list of relevant partners' channels.

This process involves WUT's proactive communication with all organizations when information is ready for dissemination. People representing an organization in a project consortium are often not responsible for communication within the organization. For this reason, we will try to establish direct contact by collecting the data of people responsible for communication in each organization. Moreover, having "short lines" of communication will allow us to keep up to date on all events that partners are organizing and participating in, and when they will be, so as to prepare and adapt to the presence on social media.

Partner's dissemination activities may include, but are not limited to: cooperation with relevant national and local media (print, radio, television, Internet), contributing to ERA FABRIC in social media, actively sharing information about project results with WUT, listing their own communication activities in a shared file and providing translations of materials for non-academic audiences in their local language. As far as possible, partners will translate press releases into their national languages and inform the WUT of their dissemination plans. Importantly, WUT is always available to support ad hoc communication.

Communication guidelines

To support and encourage partners to engage in communication activities, WUT define and provide communication and dissemination instructions. The partner's communication efforts will be actively supported by the WUT, provided that the relevant information is provided sufficiently in advance to ensure that appropriate preparations are made.

ERA FABRIC website

An attractive, user-friendly project website (www.erafabric.eu) is being developed to increase the visibility of project results to all target audiences. This website will be the main source of information about the project. Reciprocal links between partner sites will drive traffic to the project site. The project website will include:

- Detailed information on the goals and objectives of the project, project activities (including submission of public results in the relevant sections in this tab), partners, news, publications, contact details
- Social media links/buttons.

Social media

Social media will be used to share information and news about the project and redirect users to the website. The WUT-managed Twitter account ERA FABRIC will regularly publish content related to project events and results to increase its reach. Other partners

will be encouraged to reinforce posts from there. The hashtag for all social media posts will be #ERA FABRIC.

Online media platforms will be monitored to provide information on the numbers, sources, types of content and people/organizations promoting or disseminating the project's messages, thus optimizing and targeting communications to ensure maximum coverage of news or results.

PowerPoint templates

An introductory PowerPoint presentation will be created to support the partners presenting the project and ensure that all partners talk about the project in a consistent way, listing the same goals and activities and using the same terminology. Partners can then easily add slides of their own activities and contributions to the project.

Newsletter

An attractive and accessible e-newsletter will be produced and widely disseminated through the networks and communication channels of the project and partners.

Infographic

An infographic will be developed to explain a complex issue in an understandable and engaging way. The infographic will be widely promoted via newsletter and social media, always to increase the visibility of the project.

ERA FABRIC Communication and Dissemination Plan Impact

The wide scope of the project communication and dissemination activities will lead to the list of 5 communication and 6 dissemination impacts which achievement will be measured by KPIs (*Table 4*). The achievement of KPIs depends on the right execution of carefully considered pathways which are leading to them.

Table 4. Expected impacts of ERA FABRIC Communication & Dissemination Plan

Expected Impact	KPI targets	Pathways
C.1. Main online information point; communication of project news, events & results; liaisons with other initiatives, projects through links; increased awareness.	15.000 unique visitors, 2 min. average visit duration, 100.000 page views	Creating user friendly platform with interesting content.
C.2. Increasing visibility to social media; attainment of interest of active stakeholders; viral marketing by "word of mouth" through	4 social media groups, 750 accumulative followers, 1.000 accumulative posts, 250 interactions	Setting up social media groups in the most popular networks:

Expected Impact	KPI targets	Pathways
followers; direct communication mechanism with followers.		LinkedIn, Twitter, ResearchGate, YouTube.
C.3. Communication of the main project's concepts and advances in a catchy and easily understandable manner.	500 news feed posts, 1.000 interactions	Preparing interesting posts built on the project's progress in its implementation.
C.4. Communication of project news, events & results; increased awareness.	20 press releases, 500 e-newsletter (policy briefs) recipients	Preparing relevant press releases and content for policy briefs bases on the project progress
C.5. Unique branding and visual identity of the project; provision of instant information about the project; creating a unified experience for the audiences targeted; improved communication of results and information provision during events.	9 ecosystem profiles, 2 brochures and leaflets (in English and native languages), 3 e-Newsletters, 9 videos, 5 posts in EC news portals and magazines	Preparing high quality profiles of participating regions, Setting nice layouts of brochures and leaflets. Preparing videos which present the relevant to the key topic information
D.1. Increased collaboration with other relevant initiatives and networks; synergy establishment for joint activities, information exchange and dissemination; increased awareness.	8 public events organised, 12 webinars for capacity building	Organising public events in each project territory. Organisation of webinars with practical information on capacity building
D.2. Idea gathering, knowledge exchange with relevant communities and initiatives; information about latest advancements; liaisons with other initiatives; increased awareness.	10 attendances to policy gatherings, 100 to project events organised by the Consortium	Selecting the most interesting policy gatherings events and enrolment Promotion of territorial events organised within the project.
D.3. Promotion of results to scientific communities; diffusion of a new academic research agenda on related topics.	5 conference and journal papers and 10 attendances from the consortium	Selecting of relevant conferences and journal papers.

Expected Impact	KPI targets	Pathways
D.4. Validation of project's concept, findings and advancements; idea gathering and knowledge exchange; attraction of potential adopters; increased awareness.	3 thematic working groups with 500 participants, 1 survey exercise with 200 respondents	Setting up of working groups dedicated to the project topics. Preparation of the surveys and circulation among experts
D.5. Knowledge exchange; mutual validation of results; joint dissemination activities; attraction of potential partners for collaboration.	10 additional territories, 10 projects with synergies, 4 joint activities	Attracting additional territories Setting up joint activities
D.6. Communication of project news, events & results; validation of project's concept, findings and advancement; ideas' gathering and knowledge exchange; increased awareness.	40 interviews and 2 evaluation surveys involving at least 120 participants	Preparing interviews and evaluation surveys Carry out interviews and evaluation surveys.

Deliverables & Milestones

The communication, dissemination and public engagement activities includes four deliverables (*Table 5*) and one milestone (*Table 6*) which are technicalities to be reported to the funding agency.

Table 5. Deliverables

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
D7.1.	Communication and dissemination plan	WUT	R - Document, report	PU - Public	6
D7.2.	ERA FABRIC policy brief 1	WUT	DEC – Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	PU - Public	12
D7.3.	ERA FABRIC policy brief 2	WUT	DEC – Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	PU - Public	30

The detailed schedule is included in Annexes 5 & 6.

Gender and equal treatment aspects

ERA FABRIC puts special emphasis on the role of gender regarding the economic, environmental, social, ethical, technical and financial perspectives of societies in order to explore whether and how the ERA Hub model may affect or concern women and men differently.

Activities are carried out through a balanced mix between female and male researchers as well as representatives from partners. Special attention has to be paid during the implementation of WP2 and WP3 to the involvement of all genders in the thematic working groups (WP3) and in the survey activities (WP2).

Based on individual responses and preferences, ERA FABRIC aims also at investigating what gender norms, relations, or identities are relevant to the specific policies and instruments identified within WP4 and highlights social and behavioural patterns, barriers and drivers for all genders in the forthcoming ERA Hub movement.

Evidence-based analyses on gender-related peculiarities and conclusions for the relative importance and social acceptance of proposed tools to all genders are part of the dissemination activities included in WP7 as well as of the management activities.

Concerning the dissemination of ERA FABRIC results, special attention is dedicated to:

- a) reporting sample characteristics by gender, sex, and relevant intersecting variables and how information on gender identity was obtained, by avoiding over emphasising gender differences;
- b) disaggregating reported results by sex and gender and reporting all results: positive and negative;
- c) ensuring that gender variations are properly reported in tables, figures, and conclusions;
- d) referring to SAGER publication guidelines Implementation and checklist (EASE, 2016)

WP7 is built upon the integration of the gender dimension in the communication, dissemination and public engagement of the project in order to ensure gender balance in the implementation of the activities.

The gender requirements for WP 7 address gender dimension, neutrality against stereotypes in communication and dissemination activities (key messages, images, photos, videos, brand, web and social communication).

Inclusion and equal opportunities also pass through the use of language and internal and external communication that pays attention to gender differences, representing people and social and work roles in a plural and non-stereotyped way. Public communication plays a fundamental role in promoting cultural changes and in contrasting discrimination and gender stereotypes.

The communication and dissemination plan acknowledge the importance of a spoken, written and visual language suitable for the ethical objectives of communication.

ERA FABRIC, pursuant to the European Parliament Guidelines “GENDER-NEUTRAL LANGUAGE in the European Parliament” acknowledges that *gender-neutral language is a generic term covering the use of non-sexist language, inclusive language or gender-fair language. The purpose of gender-neutral language is to avoid word choices which may be interpreted as biased, discriminatory or demeaning by implying that one sex or social gender is the norm. Using gender-fair and inclusive language also helps reduce gender stereotyping, promotes social change and contributes to achieving gender equality.*

Considering English as a common project language, ERA FABRIC also adopts the United Nations “Guidelines for gender-inclusive language in English”.

Compliance with ethical principles and relevant legislations (GDPR)

Ethical principles

ERA FABRIC acknowledges that pursuant to the Grant Agreement (Article 14 – ETHICS AND VALUES 14.1 Ethics and Annex 5 specific rules), the project partners must carry out the action in compliance with:

- a) ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity as set out, for instance, in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and including, in particular, avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism or other research misconduct);
- b) applicable international, EU and national law.

Ethical dimension of the objectives, methodology and likely impact and GDPR compliance

On a general level, the project doesn't raise any ethically sensitive issue.

The handling of personal data is limited to 4 cases:

- 1) softly identifying the respondents to the online stakeholders' survey described in WP2;
- 2) softly identifying the participants in the discussions within the thematic working groups described in WP3 and WP4;
- 3) interacting with the partners and external third parties in the context of the data collection exercise for monitoring and evaluation purposes described in WP5;

- 4) interacting with stakeholders in the context of the project's communication and dissemination activities of WP7, including the creation of a web platform and social media groups.

In all the above cases, informed consent forms are prepared and withdrawn from all natural persons keeping the collection and storage of personal data at minimum. No sensitive data have to be collected and no personal data used for commercial purposes.

Regarding the web platform and the possibility of having some users registered therein, the only requirement is a valid email address for security purposes.

Compliance with GDPR will be ensured at all times.

In the above cases labelled as 1) and 3) the survey's prior information notice documents compliance and defines the perimeter and rationale of data collection in full.

In the case labelled as 2) the participants are natural persons belonging to the respective regional innovation systems of the partners and their contributions to the debates are public and do not even require anonymization/pseudo-anonymization.

In the case labelled as 4) there are indeed security reasons suggesting to store the email addresses of registered users but the requirement of identification will be stopped at the level of an email address.

The following table outlines the project activities dealing with personal data with evidence to WP, responsible partner and GDPR compliance.

Table 7. ERA FABRIC project activities dealing with personal data, responsibilities and tool/ procedure

Activity dealing with personal data	WP	Responsible partner	GDPR compliance
EU-wide online stakeholders' survey on the characteristics of knowledge ecosystems (target > 100)	2	TTP	Informed consent sheet on data processing
Identifying the participants in the discussions within the thematic working groups described	3-4	UNIST	Public debate and contributions, release in case of publication of photos, videos or other materials on the web and social networks. More information in the Communication and dissemination plan (WP7)/IPR rules

Activity dealing with personal data	WP	Responsible partner	GDPR compliance
Interacting with the partners and external third parties in the context of the data collection exercise for monitoring and evaluation purpose	5	MU	Informed consent sheet on data processing
Interacting with stakeholders in the context of the project's communication and dissemination activities of WP7, including the creation of a web platform and social media groups.	7	WUT	Identification limited to e-mail address. Release and consent to the publication and transmission of images, videos and contents. More information in the communication and dissemination plan (WP7)/IPR rules

Data Processing

ERA FABRIC acknowledges that pursuant to the Grant Agreement (Article 15.2 “Data processing by the beneficiaries”), Partners must process personal data in compliance with the applicable EU, international and national law on data protection (in particular, Regulation 2016/679).

They must ensure that personal data are:

- processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subjects;
- collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes;
- adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed;
- accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date;
- kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data is processed and processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of the data.

Partners may grant their personnel access to personal data only if it is strictly necessary for implementing, managing and monitoring the project. Partners must ensure that the personnel is under a confidentiality obligation.

Moreover, pursuant the Consortium Agreement Article 4.4 “Specific responsibilities regarding data protection”, Partners where necessary shall cooperate in order to enable one another to fulfil legal obligations arising under applicable data protection laws (the

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and relevant national data protection law applicable to said Party) within the scope of the performance and administration of the Project. In particular, Partners shall, where necessary, conclude a separate data processing, data sharing and/or joint controller agreement before any data processing or data sharing takes place.

Additional provisions and requirements are defined in the Data Management Plan (WP1 - Deliverable D1.3) including Informed consent sheet on data processing.

Personal Data Protection Compliance

Privacy accountability

The partition of the activities envisaged in the various WPs must be considered as a starting point from a GDPR perspective. In this regard, the close relationship between the processing of personal data related to the aforementioned activities and the related responsibilities, in terms of compliance with the legislation on the protection of personal data, assumes critical relevance.

Therefore, the partners establish that each WP Leader is controller pursuant art. 4 n. 7 of the GDPR with reference to the processing of personal data related to the WP they are responsible for. In fact, the responsibility each WP Leader holds over the assigned WP requires the said WP Leader to define the most effective organisational and technological measures to protect the rights and freedoms of the interested parties. Additionally, each Partner holds responsibility over the identification of the legal bases relevant to the data processing which is carried out within their own organisation. In fact, given the different legal status of the consortium partners, it would be unfeasible to define a "homogeneous" legal basis for the processing of data across WPs and Partners.

Sharing of the collected data with the Project Partners

When the Partners collect personal data, they acquire the consent from the data subjects for sharing the same data with the Project Partners.

The activities carried out within this project are all aimed at homogeneously raising awareness and giving the widest possible dissemination and therefore to obtain a solid community of interest among Quadruple Helix stakeholders.

The personal data provided, which do not fall within those indicated in Articles 9 and 10 of the GDPR, are treated exclusively in compliance with the above. And it is for this reason that a single consent for the sharing of data between the project partners is considered in line with the GDPR.

Personal data collection through forms and Privacy Notices

Whenever a personal data is collected through a form on ERA FABRIC website (directly accessible or linked in a webpage), the data subject must agree with the storage and

processing of their personal data in accordance with the ERA FABRIC Privacy Policy and must provide therein their consent to their personal data processing for the purposes and terms indicated in the linked Privacy Notice provided by the member of the ERA FABRIC Consortium responsible for that specific data processing.

References

1. GRANT AGREEMENT Project 101094821 – ERA FABRIC, including Annex 5 “Specific rules”.
2. Grant Application Project 101094821 – ERA FABRIC - Horizon-Widera-2022-ERA-01 - Description of the action (DoA) Part A and Part B.
3. [EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025](#) objectives and actions to make significant progress by 2025 towards a gender-equal Europe.
4. IPR helpdesk brochure "[Making the Most of Your H2020 Project. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation](#)".
5. The [EU Guide to Science Communication](#), a couple of short videos about science communication in general, and some specific tips on how to improve your communication efforts.
6. [Quick guide and tools for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation](#)
7. The brochure [Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants](#) which gives you an overview of best practices and a check list on how to build a communication strategy.
8. [ERA Progress Reports](#) - state of play of ERA and progress made on its implementation by EU and associated countries (2018)
9. [European Research Area Policy Agenda](#) – Overview of actions for the period 2022-2024, European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation Directorate A – ERA & Innovation Unit A.2 – ERA governance and Implementation
10. [The Ljubljana Declaration](#) on Gender Equality in Research and Innovation presented by the Slovenian Presidency to Member States in the Competitiveness Council of 28 September 2021
11. [She Figures Handbook \(2021\)](#) - Gender in research and innovation: statistics and indicators Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (European Commission), 24/11/2021
12. [The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity Revised Edition](#), ALLEA - All European Academies, Berlin 2017
13. [Horizon Europe Article 19 - Regulation \(EU\) 2021/695](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 April 2021 establishing Horizon Europe
14. [European Union Regulation no. 679/2016 for the protection of personal data - “GDPR”](#) (May 25, 2018)

15. [SAGER publication guideline](#) (EASE, 2016) - The Sex and Gender Equity in Research guidelines and checklist
16. [GENPORT](#), community sourced Internet Portal on gender and science, project funded by the European Union FP7-SCIENCE-IN-SOCIETY-2012-1 programme.
17. [GENDER-NEUTRAL LANGUAGE in the European Parliament](#) - guidelines
18. United Nations [Guidelines for gender-inclusive language in English](#)
19. ERA FABRIC Consortium Agreement - Version 3, 9/12/2022.
20. The [Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects](#), Version 1.1, 07 January 2020.

ANNEX 1. ERA FABRIC project visualization

Logotypes

Project Logotypes

EU logotypes

**Funded by
the European Union**

**Funded by
the European Union**

National languages

**Finansowane przez
Unię Europejską**

Partner logotypes

Templates

Documents

Page

Letter

Presentation

Title of the presentation

Title of the second slide

The Calibi font is a draft font and is guaranteed to be widely used.
The font has many different dialect variants that are needed by all partners.
We strongly recommend the LIGHT variety.

The Lovelo font is a font that we use in our logo,
but it can also appear in the presentation as a special element.

**THE LOVELO FONT IS A SOLEMN DISTINGUISHING FEATURE.
IF YOU NEED TO USE THE LOVELO FONT FOR COMMERCIAL PURPOSES,
WE RECOMMEND USING EXTENDED SOFTWARE SUCH AS CANVA.**

Logo usage instruction

Primary / basic version:

The icon: WEAVE

The weave symbolizes the connection between partners and at the same time is a guarantee of perseverance.

The icon can be used independently and as a graphic theme.

Logo usage instruction

Primary / basic version:

The font used is LOVELO with Black type.
The font has several variations.

Color characteristics:
#2A3276
RGB 42/50/118
CMYK 100/94/22/10

Logo usage instruction

Variations of logo:

Logo usage instruction

- In order to popularize the brand, we want each partner to be able to propose the use of the logo as a patron. The logo should be used wherever possible.
- We ask you to report the use of the logotype on other materials to the following e-mail address: media@erafabric.eu
- We must add the EU logo to our activities in accordance with the agreement:

17.2 Visibility — European flag and funding statement

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

ANNEX 2. ERA FABRIC WWW Platform

Structure

Homepage

- **ERA Hub**
Clarification what is the ERA hub concept about
- **Sign up/ Sign in**
Brief explanation: Short registration/ login procedure to fulfil self-assessment tool due to quality control of the data provided
- **Newsletter**
Brief explanation: Newsletter submission request

News & event section

- **Latest news**
Brief explanation: Updates about the latest activities and achievements of the project
- **Events & webinars (MS Teams, click meeting, zoom)**
Brief explanation: Information about the events scheduled or done including agenda, presentations, outcomes, registration etc.

Resources

- **Territorial Profiles**
Brief explanation: Profiles of territories based on the semi-automated data collection database and self-assessment tool
- **Self-assessment tool**
Brief explanation: Self-assessment tool to gather the information about territories based on the project developed methodology
- **Working groups**
 - Sustainable manufacturing
 - Bio-based circular economy
 - Clean renewable energy*Brief explanation:* News & updates about the performance of these three groups
- **Policy toolbox**
 - Case studies
 - Tested policy measures
 - Policy innovative measures
 - ERA Hub theory of change*Brief explanation:* Policy toolbox items
- **Multimedia**
 - Movies
 - Others*Brief explanation:* Different sort of multimedia

- **Policy briefs**
Brief explanation: Reports of major project achievements
- **E-Brochures & E-Leaflets**
Brief explanation: Support to an increase of the awareness and promotion of ERA FABRIC
- **Manuals**
 - IT syllabus for webinars
 - Self-assessment tool*Brief explanation:* Manuals explaining how to use project tools

Associated

- Territories
Brief explanation: Territories & communities attracted to the project
- Initiatives
Brief explanation: Project and clusters attracted to the project

About

- ERA FABRIC project
Brief explanation: Brief information about the project
- Project Partners
Brief explanation: Brief information about the project partners
- Expert profiles
Brief explanation: Brief information about key people involved in the project
- Contact & FAQ
Brief explanation: Contact details & answers to frequently asked questions
- Privacy policy
Brief explanation: Privacy policy rules
- Legal notice
Brief explanation: Mainly disclaimers

Social media

- LinkedIn
 - ResearchGate
 - Twitter
 - YouTube
- Brief explanation:*
- Social media section

Technology

WWW Hosting

dhosting

- flexible scaling of resources
- optimisation for wordpress
- litespeed as a web server
- We already have and pay for an account and domain name there

- very good support
- backups
- fast SSD drives
- redis included in the package
- no site limits

More: <https://dhosting.pl/elastyczny-hosting.html>

Newsletter

GetResponse

- 1000/2500 contacts
- no limit on messages sent
- message creator
- A/B testing
- click tracking
- personalized templates
- dark mode
- 24h support
- landing page
- chat (live chat)
- extensive analytics
- many integrations
- more: <https://www.getresponse.com/pricing>

Calendar

Sugar calendar

- licencja na 3 / nielimitowane witryny
- integracja z google calendar
- bilety
- wydarzenia cykliczne

More: <https://sugarcalendar.com/pricing/>

Analytics

The platform analytics relies on Google Analytics which is a web analytics service offered by Google that tracks and reports website traffic.

Print screens

ANNEX 3. Social media

LinkedIn

Twitter

YouTube

ResearchGate

ANNEX 4. Events calendar

Order	Date	Title of the event	Place	Participant	Target audience	Internal/ External	Onsite/ Online	Planned/ ad hoc	Contribution/ results
1									
2									
3									

*Internal – ERA FABRIC event/ External – organized by others

ANNEX 5. Communication activities time schedule

Communication activities	Activity name	Projet period in months																														
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	
C.1.	Project's web platform																															
	1.1. Design & develop an intuitive and responsive project's web platform; search engine optimisation.																															
	1.2. Regular update of the web platform content; watch web platform's analytics to measure impact and provide content of interest.																															
	1.3. Regular update of the web platform content; clear visibility of results, demo/application material in an interactive way.																															
C.2.	Social Media Presence																															
	2.1. Establish a presence in social media. Reproduce relevant content and monitor relevant hashtags; upload public material; follow influencers of the domain; engage to other projects and initiatives.																															
	2.2. Promote project's outcomes and events; interact with followers to get feedback; answer on comments and private messages on the various channels; upload public material; reproduce relevant content and monitor relevant hashtags.																															
	2.3. Promote project's outcomes and events; interact with followers to get feedback; answer on comments and private messages on the various channels; upload public material; reproduce relevant content (more sporadically).																															
C.3.	Project's news feed																															
	3.1. Deploy project's news feed; provide news feed posts related to project's positioning and interim achievements.																															
	3.2. Provide frequent posts to initiate discussions on specific issues relevant to the project to receive feedback.																															
	3.3. Publish frequent news feed posts to demonstrate and promote the project's results.																															
C.4.	Traditional Media																															
	4.1. Press release to announce the project's launch and progress.																															
	4.2. Press releases to announce the significant events/results.																															
	4.3. Press releases to promote the policy value and societal benefits of the project's results.																															
C.5.	Communication Material																															
	5.1. Design logo & graphic identity; prepare brochure, leaflet, first policy brief and promotional video.																															
	5.2. Revise brochure, leaflet and release new policy brief; post to EU publications (e.g., Cordis News, Research EU magazines etc.).																															
	5.3. Prepare final brochure, leaflet, policy brief and video demonstrators; post to EU publications.																															

ANNEX 6. Dissemination activities time schedule

Dissemination activities	Activity name	Project period in months																														
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	
D.1. Organisation of public events both offline and online																																
1.1. Organisation of workshops/seminars alongside project meetings																																
1.2. Organisation of workshops/seminars and training events (webinars)																																
D.2. Participation in third party events (EU and national policy gatherings)																																
2.1. Presentation of project scope; Interaction with participants.																																
2.2. Presentation of project results; Interaction with participants.																																
D.3. Participation in scientific conferences and academic events																																
3.1. Publication of position papers; Organisation of special sessions.																																
3.2. Publication of interim results; Organisation of special sessions.																																
D.4. Community Building / Engagement with local stakeholders																																
4.1. Creation of thematic working groups.																																
4.2. Discussions within the thematic working groups; sharing of early results.																																
4.3. Video demonstrations of activities and sharing of the final project results.																																
D.5. Collaboration and Synergies with sister Projects and ERA Hubs																																
5.1. Synergy identification; establishment of contact points; exchange of ideas & intentions.																																
5.2. Periodic bilateral exchange of news & results, joint presence at events.																																
5.3. Joint engagement in events and initiatives.																																
D.6. Internal dissemination through Partners Networks																																
6.1. Project's links & news in partners' websites, social media accounts, newsletters.																																
6.2. Inclusion of project' results in partners' events.																																
6.3. Demonstration of use of results in partners' regions.																																
D.7. Contributions to standards																																
7.1. State of the art analysis.																																
7.2. Definition of criteria and conditions for quality assessment.																																
7.3. Finalisation and public presentation of the quality scheme.																																

ANNEX 7. KPIs monitoring tool

	Current	Targets
C.1. Main online information point; communication of project news, events & results; liaisons with other initiatives, projects through links; increased awareness.		
unique visitors	0	15 000
average visit duration (minutes)	0	2
page views	0	100 000
C.2. Increasing visibility to social media; attainment of interest of active stakeholders; viral marketing by “word of mouth” through followers; direct communication mechanism with followers.		
social media groups		4
accumulative followers		750
accumulative posts		1 000
interactions		250
C.3. Communication of the main project’s concepts and advances in a catchy and easily understandable manner.		
news feed posts		500
interactions		1 000
C.4. Communication of project news, events & results; increased awareness.		
press releases		20
e-newsletter (policy briefs) recipients		500
C.5. Unique branding and visual identity of the project; provision of instant information about the project; creating a unified experience for the audiences targeted; improved communication of results and information provision during events.		
ecosystem profiles		9
brochures and leaflets (in English and native languages):		2
CZ		2
DE		2
ES		2
HR		2
IT		2
NO		2
PL		2
PT		2
RO		2
e-Newsletters		3
posts in EC news portals and magazines		5
D.1. Increased collaboration with other relevant initiatives and networks; synergy establishment for joint activities, information exchange and dissemination; increased awareness.		
public events organised		8
webinars for capacity building		12
D.2. Idea gathering, knowledge exchange with relevant communities and initiatives; information about latest advancements; liaisons with other initiatives; increased awareness.		
attendances to policy gatherings		10
to project events organised by the Consortium		100
D.3. Promotion of results to scientific communities; diffusion of a new academic research agenda on related topics.		
conference and journal papers		5
attendances from the consortium		10
D.4. Validation of project’s concept, findings and advancements; idea gathering and knowledge exchange; attraction of potential adopters; increased awareness.		
3 thematic working groups with participants		500
1 survey exercise with Respondents		200
D.5. Knowledge exchange; mutual validation of results; joint dissemination activities; attraction of potential partners for collaboration.		
additional territories		10
projects with synergies		10
joint activities		4
D.6. Communication of project news, events & results; validation of project’s concept, findings and advancement; ideas’ gathering and knowledge exchange; increased awareness.		
interviews		40
2 evaluation surveys involving participants		120